

FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROSPHERES BASED FORMULATION OF RACECADOTRIL

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Abstract: Racecadotril loaded microspheres has been prepared as drug targeting formulation and the controlled release. The Preformulation studies it is found that the organoleptic properties of Racecadotril comply as reported. Light yellow, bitter, odorless, amorphous powder of Racecadotril was insoluble in water, soluble in 0.1N HCl and freely soluble in methanol and slightly soluble in ethanol and 0.1N NaOH. Melting point was observed at 88-90 °C and λ_{max} at 231 nm. Standard calibration curve was prepared using concentration range 5- 25 ug/ml and linearity equation as $y = 0.025x + 0.015$ with $R^2 = 0.997$. Partition coefficient was found 2.21 ± 0.001 . Drug Racecadotril was also compatible with used excipients. Five different formulations were prepared by o/w modified emulsification method using different concentration of sodium alginate and fixed amount (100mg) of Racecadotril and magnesium stearate (1g) and CaCl₂ (2.5 g). Evaluation of prepared floating microspheres were found yield between 69.31- 82.87 %, mean particle size between 270-344 μm and Drug Entrapment between 68.01- 82.19%. On the basis of various parameters of evaluation of microspheres formulations, the **F-1** has greater yield 82.87 % and its Drug Entrapment was 82.19%, particle size (270 μm), and highest drug release was 93.36 %. SEM analysis also indicated that Microsphere batch F-1 had smooth surface and regular in shape. Kinetic modeling revealed that microsphere batch F-1 was followed first order kinetics.

Keywords: Racecadotril, Microspheres, Preformulation, Emulsification, Modeling, Excipients

INTRODUCTION

Non-compliance of medication is a terrible traffic jam for successful management results in a large number of diseases¹. Among the factors threatening patient adherence, a high number of daily doses, the duration of the condition (acute versus chronic) and the transition to chronification as well as adverse side effects pose severe challenges². The World Health

Organization (WHO) has reported that in countries in the Global North the concordance to long-term therapies stands at about 50%³. The administration of properly designed long-acting formulations reduces the frequency of required doses needed to achieve and maintain therapeutic efficacy, improving patient compliance and overall reducing unwanted side effects⁴. Furthermore, depot formulations could be particularly beneficial for classes of patients that are unable to adhere to treatment regimens, such as those suffering from psychiatric disorders⁵. Microspheres has been acknowledged as drug targeting formulation and the controlled release⁶. Mucoadhesion has been a topic of interest in the design of drug delivery system to prolong the residence time of the dosage form at the site of application or absorption and to facilitate absorption intimate contact of the dosage form with underlying surface to improve the bioavailability of drugs⁷. Several studies has been reported drug delivery system in the form of tablets, films, patches, and gels for oral, buccal, nasal, ocular, and topical routes⁸. The significant number of annual accepted novel parenteral molecular entities, proteins, antibodies and peptides, but also small molecules characterized either by flux in the GIT or high first-pass metabolism, encourages the design of more versatile drug delivery technologies⁹.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Organoleptic evaluation: It was the assessment of sensory organs e.g. appearance, taste, odor etc.

Preparation of Microsphere of Racecadotril: The microspheres were prepared by using modified emulsification method as reported by Rahman et al. The drug was dispersed in aqueous solution of sodium alginate (2.5-4.5 g) with magnesium stearate (0-1 g). The solution was emulsified in liquid paraffin containing span 80 using a mechanical stirrer at 1700 rpm for 1 h. After this, calcium chloride (2.5g) solution (in isopropyl alcohol) was added to the emulsion at the rate of 2 ml/min. The emulsion was stirred for 10 more min. Microspheres formed in organic phase were removed by filtration and washed with hexane to remove liquid paraffin. Microspheres were then vacuum dried for 48 h.

Evaluation of Microspheres:

Percentage yield: The percentage yield of microspheres was determined from the ratio of solidified total microspheres to the solid material used in the inner phase multiplied by 100.

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \text{Practical yield/theoretical Yield} \times 100$$

Particle size analysis: Particle size analysis plays an important role in determining the release characteristics and property. The sizes of microspheres were measured by using an optical microscope and mean particle size was calculated by measuring nearly 200 particles with the help of a calculated ocular micrometer.

Percentage encapsulation efficiency: 20 mg microsphere sample was dissolved in 20 ml of phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and kept for overnight. The solution was filtered to remove exhausted microspheres. UV absorbance of the solution was measured using a UV spectrophotometer at 231 nm. Percentage encapsulation efficiency was determined for all batches using below.

$$\text{Encapsulation efficiency} = (\text{actual amount of Ibuprofen in sample/theoretical amount of Ibuprofen}) \times 100.$$

Shape and Surface Characterization of by Scanning Electron Microscopy: From the formulated batches of microspheres formulations which possessed a correct equilibrium between the buoyancy and the percentage release were inspected for surface morphology and shape using SEM, JEOL, JSM-670F Japan. Sample was fixed on carbon tape and fine gold sputtering was applied in a high vacuum evaporator. The acceleration voltage was set at 3.0 KV during scanning. Microphotographs were taken on different magnification and higher magnification (500X) was used for surface morphology.

In-vitro Drug Release Studies: The drug release rate from microspheres was performed using the USP type II (Electro Lab.) dissolution paddle assembly. A weighed amount of microspheres equivalent to 100 mg drug were dispersed in 900 ml of 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred at 100 rpm. One ml sample was withdrawn at predetermined intervals and filtered and equal volume of dissolution medium was replaced in the vessel after each withdrawal to maintain sink condition. The collected samples were treated with methyl orange

and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 231nm to determine the concentration of drug present in the dissolution medium.

Drug Release Kinetic Data Analysis: Drug release kinetics study of Racecadotril from the microspheres the drug release data was fixed to following equations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organoleptic evaluation:

Table No. 3: Organoleptic property of Racecadotril

Color	Light yellow
Odor	Odorless
Taste:	Bitter
Physical state	Solid Amorphous Powder

Solubility: Solubility studies of Racecadotril have been done in various solvent. Found that a solubility of Racecadotril is good in a Methanol solution.

Table No. 4: Solubility studies of Racecadotril different solvent

S. No.	Solvent used	Solubility
1.	Water	Insoluble
2.	0.1N HCl	Soluble
3.	Ethanol	Slightly Soluble
4.	Methanol	Freely Soluble
5.	0.1N NaOH	Slightly Soluble

Melting Point determination: Melting point determination of the obtained drug sample. The melting point of the drug sample range of the drug is 88 -90 °C.

Partition Coefficient measurement: In the case Chloroform and water, Partition Coefficient measurement of drug sample is 2.21 ± 0.001 .

$$P_o/w = C \text{ chloroform}/C \text{ water}$$

Determination of λ_{\max} by UV-Visible Spectroscopy Procedure: Accurately weighed 10mg of Racecadotril separately and dissolved in 10ml of 0.1NHCL in 10ml of volumetric flask and prepared appropriate dilution to prepare it to a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ make adequate of sample with conc. range of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Racecadotril and calculate the spectrum of this solution was run in 200-400 nm range in U.V spectrophotometer. The λ_{\max} found for Racecadotril is 231.0 nm as shown in figure below:

Figure 2: The λ_{\max} found for Racecadotril

Figure No. 3: Calibration Curve of Racecadotril

Statistical Data for Linearity

Table No. 6: Statistical Data for Linearity

S. No.	Parameter	Remark
1	Linearity Range	5-25 μ g/ml
2	Regression Equation	0.025 x + 0.015
3	Correlation Coefficient	0.997

Formulation Microsphere of Racecadotril

Table No. 7: Prepared Formulations of the Microspheres

Formulation Code	Drug (mg)	Amount of sodium alginate (g)	Amount of magnesium stearate (g)	Amount of CaCl ₂ (g)
F1	100	2.5	1	2.5
F2	100	3	1	2.5
F3	100	3.5	1	2.5
F4	100	4	1	2.5
F5	100	4.5	1	2.5

Evaluation of Microsphere of Racecadotril

Particle size analysis: Particle size was determined by Optical microscopy method. It plays important role in floating ability and release of drug from Microsphere. If size of Microspheres is less than 500 μ m release rate of drug will be high white Microspheres ranging between 200 μ m - 500 μ m, the release rate will be in sustained manner. Average particle size of Racecadotril microsphere was in range 270-344 μ m as shown in Table:

Percentage Yield: Percentage yield of various formulations was determined by weighing the Microspheres after drying. The percentage yield of different formulation was in range of 69.31 - 82.87 % as shown in Table.

Drug Entrapment: The drug entrapment efficacies of “various formulations were in range of 68.01- 82.19 % w/w as shown in Table. Drug entrapment efficacies slightly decrease with increase sodium alginate content in Microspheres. This is due to the permeation characteristics of sodium alginate that could ease the diffusion of part of entrapped drug to surrounding medium during preparation of Racecadotril microsphere.

Table No. 10: Percentage Yield for Different Formulation

Formulation	Percent Yield (%)	Drug entrapment (% w/w)	Mean particle size (μm)
F1	82.87	82.19	270 ± 14
F2	78.53	76.59	276 ± 21
F3	76.47	72.23	278 ± 23
F4	71.56	70.76	284 ± 25
F5	69.31	68.01	301 ± 24

Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) study of optimized Microsphere batch F-1**Figure 4: SEM study of optimized Microsphere batch F-1****Drug Release Studies:****Table No. 11: *In-vitro* drug release study of Racecadotril loaded microsphere**

Time (hr)	% of Drug Release				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
0.5	46.49	37.00	34.86	30.86	27.87
1.0	60.56	52.67	48.71	42.57	38.36
1.5	70.69	63.57	61.32	54.32	49.33
2.0	76.17	70.99	67.89	62.83	57.57
3.0	81.24	76.43	72.82	70.81	67.71
4.0	84.67	82.24	75.63	79.43	74.53
6.0	88.21	85.74	81.07	82.17	79.14
8.0	93.36	88.79	84.74	83.74	81.17

Graph of release study of formulation

Figure 5: In-vitro drug release study of Racecadotril loaded microspheres

Kinetic Modeling of Drug Release from Microsphere Formulations (F-1)

Figure 6: Zero order kinetics of optimized formulation F-1

Figure 7: First order kinetics of optimized formulation F-1

Figure 8: Higuchi model of kinetics of optimized formulation F-1

Figure 9: Peppas- Korsmeyer model of kinetics of optimized formulation F-1

Table No. 13: Study of release mechanism by curve fitting analysis

Formulation	Zero Order (R ²)	First Order (R ²)	Higuchi (R ²)	Peppas- Korsmeyer (R ²)
F-1	0.749	0.948	0.875	0.913

Observation: Optimized formulation F-1 followed the first order kinetics so the best fitted model is first order kinetic model.

Accelerated Stability Studies: There were no major changes in appearance, Drug entrapment and *in-vitro* drug release.

Table No. 14: Table for Accelerated Stability Studies

Formulation	Appearance	Drug entrapment	<i>In-vitro</i> drug release
F-1	No Change	80.29	92.46

CONCLUSION

Drug absorption in the gastrointestinal tract is a highly variable process. Microspheres are promising to be a potential approach for gastric retention enhances the bioavailability and controlled delivery of various therapeutic agents. Significant attempts have been made worldwide to explore these systems according to patient requirements, both in terms of therapeutic efficacy and compliance. Microspheres as gastro retentive dosage forms precisely control the release rate of target drug to a specific site and facilitate an enormous impact on health care. These systems also provide tremendous opportunities in the designing of new controlled and delayed release oral formulations, thus extending the frontier of futuristic pharmaceutical development. Furthermore, recent innovations in pharmaceutical investigation will surely provide real prospects for establishment of novel and effective means in the development of these promising drug delivery systems.

In-vitro data obtained for microspheres of Racecadotril showed good incorporation efficiency, and prolonged drug release. Microspheres of different size and drug content could be obtained by varying the formulation variables. From the results it can be concluded that the drug release from the floating microspheres controlled by the polymer proportion

CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS

There are no conflicts of interests.

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